

Deliverable D8 within 19ENG08

- Good Practice Guide for traceable efficiency determination of devices under test on nacelle test benches -

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Disclaimer

Any mention of commercial products within this report is for information only; it does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the partners in this project.

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1 Introduction

In March 2022, the European Commission proposed a “joint European action for more affordable, secure and sustainable energy” [1]. To boost humans’ step towards carbon neutral, wind energy has a great potential to speed up this green transition. To effectively harvest the wind energy and reduce the infrastructure costs, the rated power of single wind turbine is trending above 10 MW. For a wind turbine of this size, accurately measuring the efficiency is becoming more important ever, as even a small amount of measurement deviation represents an enormous amount of potential energy. A traceable efficiency determination is not only a great help to improve the turbine design, but also to maximize the energy production in the field by optimising the control methods [2].

Therefore, a traceable and comparable efficiency determination method for nacelle drive trains and their components on nacelle test benches (NTBs) is required. Traceability in efficiency means that all measurement variables involved for efficiency determination must be validated by being compared to the national standard to obtain their sensitivity corrections and the measurement uncertainties (MU). This calibration includes not only the sensors for torque, rotational speed, currents, and voltages in the test bench, but also the complete measurement chains. After calibration, during the measurement procedure, certain steps and rules should be followed to ensure the sensors are working close to the calibration conditions. In this way, the measured efficiency can be trusted with in the guaranteed uncertainty interval.

So far, there are no internationally accepted methods or standards for the efficiency determination of wind turbines on test benches. Currently existing method to determine the efficiency of electrical machines, such as standards for the efficiency determination of rotating electrical machines, an alternative back-to-back method, a calorimetric efficiency determination method and iso-efficiency contours were investigated and introduced in this report. A lack of non-aerodynamic, standardised, and easily reproducible efficiency determination methods was revealed. Based on this information, a new efficiency determination method for nacelles and their components on test benches was developed. This new method is based on calibrated mechanical and electrical power measurement systems. It was presented including individual pre-tests, zero signal determination and load cycles. The concept itself and the practicability of the measurement procedure has been evaluated throughout three extensive measurement campaigns in cooperation with industrial partners.

This report is the base for all measurements within WP4 and therefore the main output of the project. The exemplary results of the efficiency determination from these measurement campaigns are presented. This new method has promising potential to indicate the most desirable operation range of the test device and to determine the efficiency traceability.

1.1 Glossary

- Calibration: operation that, under specified conditions, in a first step, establishes a relation between the quantity values with measurement uncertainties provided by measurement standards and corresponding indications with associated measurement uncertainties and, in a second step, uses this information to establish a relation for obtaining a measurement result from an indication (VIM 2.39).
- Transfer standard: calibrated and very well-known transducer, which is used to trace on-site measurement to the national standard.
- In-situ calibration: it relies on the comparison between a test bench sensor with a transfer standard directly during operation. The transfer standard is usually a state of the art reference sensor that has been calibrated and well-studied in a national metrology institute (NMI) with proved measurement uncertainty.
- Zero signal: offset value of a measuring device in non-loaded condition. The zero signal is used to tare all measurement signals of the following load cycle.
- Load profile: range of load applied on a measuring device during operation.

- Measurement uncertainty: non-negative parameter characterising the dispersion of the quality values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used (VIM 2.26).
- Traceability: it involves verifying the accuracy of a measurement by comparing it to a higher calibration reference standard, thus accounting for all uncertainties and ensuring a precise representation of the object being measured
- Nacelle test bench: a facility used to test a wind turbine and the components, simulating real-world conditions to assess performance, durability, and safety before deployment

1.2 Symbols and their meaning

Important symbols and their meaning regarding the efficiency determination on NTBs are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptions of the measurement parameters

Symbol	Unit	Description
$e_{P_{me}\%}$	%	The relative averaging error using the adapted expression of mechanical power determination.
η	-	Drivetrain efficiency
$i_{1...3}$	A	Transient phase current
M	N m	Torque measurement result
M_s	N m	Measured torque value before taring
M_{zero}	N m	Averaging of measured torque zero signals
n	min ⁻¹	Shaft rotational speed
N_{res}	-	Number of shaft revolutions used for power calculation
N_{zero}	-	Number of angle positions measured for static zero offset
P_{el}	W	Total effective power of all three phases
$P_{el,p1...3}$	W	Effective power of each phase
P_{in}	W	System input power
P_{me}	W	Mechanical power
$P_{me,ad}$	W	Mechanical power calculated using the adapted expression
P_{out}	W	System output power
T_{el}	s	Electrical power measurement interval
T_{me}	s	Mechanical power measurement interval
U	-	Absolute expanded uncertainty ($k=2$)
W	-	Relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$)

2 Measurement set-up and preparation

Compared to efficiency measurement in the field, the measurement of wind turbine’s efficiency on a NTB is reproduceable and less time consuming. More importantly, there is enough space to install the necessary sensors at varies measurement locations. In the following, an NTB set-up with calibrated sensors are presented.

2.1 NTB Set-up

As showed in Figure 1, an NTB usually contains an electrical motor as the prime mover to create high dynamic torque loads and rotational speeds. The maximum torque applicable at the test bench is normally in the MN·m range with a rotational speed lower than 30 min^{-1} . The non-torque loading (NTL) unit is a servo hydraulic system that provides forces and bending moments to the drivetrain. It is located between the prime mover and the device under test (DUT).

Figure 1: NTB at CWD of RWTH University including FVA nacelle. Modified based on [3].

In Figure 2, the set-up including all designated measuring points is represented in form of an equivalent circuit diagram. The generator produces 690 V as the line-to-line voltage on its secondary side, and this voltage is then increased to 10 kV as the line-to-line voltage on the primary side by the transformer. For system efficiency determinations, the mechanical input power can be measured at the low speed shaft (LSS), while the electrical power measured at the grid output. For components efficiency such as the gearbox (if the DUT is not a direct drive nacelle), the converter and the transformer, additional measurement points can be placed at the high speed shaft (HSS) after the gearbox, and at the generator and converter outputs.

*Currents and Voltages are effective values of the 3 phase system

Figure 2: Equivalent circuit diagram of the test set-up with full size converter at RWTH Aachen.

2.2 Measurement sensors and calibration

The NTBs are usually equipped with a diverse array of sensors designed to monitor various measurement parameters. The most relevant sensors for efficiency determination are mainly the torque and the rotational speed sensors used for mechanical input power, as well as the current and the voltage transducers for electrical output power.

2.2.1 In-situ calibration

To improve the measurement accuracy and evaluate the measurement quality, all sensors used for efficiency determination should be correctly calibrated in order to establish the traceability chain to the national standards. For this use case, the so called in-situ calibration would be the most suitable method. An in-situ calibration relies on the comparison between an NTB sensor with a transfer standard directly during operation. The transfer standard is generally a state-of-the-art reference sensor that has been calibrated and well studied at a National Metrology Institute (NMI) or at an Accredited Calibration Laboratory, with proven measurement uncertainty. By installing the additional transfer standard on the test bench, the stand-alone reference system measures the signal parallel with the NTB existing measurement system for calibration.

Comparing to uninstalling the NTB sensors and have them calibrated in external laboratory (external calibration), in-situ calibration can deliver the following advantages:

- Calibration under real life conditions involving the influence of temperature changes, friction loss (torque measurement), parasitic loads, EMC, etc.
- Simultaneously calibration of mechanical and electrical sensors within the same measurement campaign.
- Calibrate not only the sensors alone but also the complete measurement chains including signal transmission and data processing.

2.2.2 Mechanical power transfer standard

The developed transfer standard for mechanical power consists of a 5 MN m torque transfer standard (TTS) and an inclinometer for rotational speed measurement (Figure 3).

The utilized TTS possesses a measuring capacity of 5 MN m. However, its calibration extends only up to 1.1 MN m, primarily due to the absence of suitable torque calibration options [4]. Within this range, its performance is relying on the linear calibration curve for clockwise torque. The measurement uncertainty above 1.1 MN m is projected by extrapolating calibration data obtained from various partial ranges. The anticipated expanded relative measurement uncertainty for 5 MN m is calculated to be $10.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$ [5].

In the meantime, a micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) inclinometer integrated into the current TTS is chosen as the appropriate sensor type due to its capacity for angle measurement without requiring a stator. The stator-less rotational speed measurement is accomplished by tracking the rotational angle of the drive train over time. The inclinometer used has undergone static calibration at PTB and has been verified to possess an expanded measurement uncertainty of 0.01° . Under rotating measurement conditions, additional dynamic influences are analysed as detailed in [6]. For the determination of rotational speed, the signal processing method and the measurement uncertainty associated with time measurement are considered as outlined in [7]. Overall, the inclinometer can attain a relative measurement uncertainty of 0.018 % at 4.5 min^{-1} .

The detailed calibration procedure of the two transfer standards can be found in the project deliverables D2: Report for traceable rotational speed measurement [8] and D3: Report for traceable torque measurement [9], and the in-situ calibration procedure of the NTB mechanical measurement system using the transfer standard for mechanical power is presented in the D4: Good Practice Guide on the calibration procedure for traceable mechanical power measurement [10].

Figure 3: Transfer standard for mechanical power measurement consisting of a 5 MN m TTS and an inclinometer to calibrate mechanical power measurement in NTBs.

2.2.3 Electrical power transfer standard

The reference power measurement system (RPMS) is utilized for the in-situ calibration of the electrical power measurement system (EPMS) within the test benches. It consists of a commercial multi-channel power analyser, precision current transducers, and high-voltage dividers. The multi-channel power analyzer, the LMG 671 (depicted in Figure 4, bottom) manufactured by ZES Zimmer, is engineered for simultaneous and synchronized measurement of narrow- and broadband values, as well as harmonics and interharmonics up to the 2000th order. At the power frequency, the accuracy of power measurement is $\pm(0.015\%$ of the measured value $+0.01\%$ of maximum peak value) [11].

The precision current transducers, model 2000 A (PCT2000/DL2000ID) from Danisense and ZES Zimmer, operate on a contact-free, closed-loop, flux gate-based current measurement principle. They exhibit exceptional linearity ($\pm 0.0001\%$) and operate effectively across the entire industrial temperature range, making them well-suited for use as a transfer standard in NTBs. The accuracy specification for both amplitude and phase varies with frequency. In the frequency range from DC up to 10 Hz, the amplitude accuracy is $\pm 0.0007\%$ of the nominal input current root mean square (RMS) [12].

The precision wideband high-voltage divider, the HST 12-3 (found in Figure 4, top left), also from ZES Zimmer, can measure up to 20 kV peak (16.8 kV RMS) across frequencies ranging from DC up to 300 kHz. The divider ratio is 4000, with an amplitude error of $\pm 0.05\%$ (at 50 Hz) and a phase shift of $\pm 0.04^\circ$ (at 50 Hz) [13].

The in-situ calibration procedure of the NTB's electrical measurement system using the transfer standards is presented in the D6: Good Practice Guide on the calibration procedure for traceable electrical power measurement [14].

Figure 4: RPMS consisting of a commercial power analyser (bottom), a high voltage divider (top left), and precision current transducers (top right) to calibrate the electrical power measurement in NTBs.

2.3 Synchronisation

To ensure precise efficiency, it is crucial to measure all parameters simultaneously or, in practical terms, with minimal time misalignment. The fundamental principle of synchronization is elaborated upon in [15], and an overview of commonly employed synchronization technologies can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of commonly used synchronisation technologies

Synchronisation technology	Ethernet (NTP)	Ethernet (PTPv2)	IRIG-B	EtherCAT	IEEE1394b FireWire
Accuracy	1 ms to 50 ms	< 1 μ s	< 1 ms to 100 ns	< 1 μ s	< 1 μ s
Wireless connection	Possible	Possible	Possible	n/a	n/a

As in the signal evaluation process in section 4.2, the efficiency is determined over several number of shaft revolutions. All the listed synchronization technologies have neglectable accuracies compared to the averaging interval, and therefore suitable for synchronizing mechanical and electrical power assessment within the test bench.

In situations where synchronization through a shared time protocol is not feasible, a function generator can serve to generate reference pulse signals at the start and end of measurement curves, which can be fed to each data acquisition (DAQ) system. During post-processing, data can be manually synchronised by aligning the reference pulse across all distributed DAQ systems. However, it is important to acknowledge that manual synchronization demands additional effort and may result in quality variations.

It is to note that even when DAQ systems were correctly synchronised at the beginning of measurements, an increased time offset can still be observed, particularly after prolonged continuous measurements. This offset arises from the accumulated clock systematic error among different DAQ systems. For instance, a channel with a 1 kHz sampling rate may have an actual time step of 0.9999 ms instead of an exact 1 ms. After three hours of continuous measurement, the accumulated time offset could be approximately 1 second. To mitigate this issue, the best approach is to employ synchronisation via a shared time protocol and record the absolute time vector rather than solely relying on the relative time vector.

3 Efficiency determination method

Efficiency evaluation for electrical machines can be accomplished through either direct or indirect methods. Direct efficiency determination relies on measuring mechanical and electrical power, which involves assessing input and output power. On the other hand, the indirect efficiency determination method involves measuring electrical power and power losses, specifically the summation of losses. Standard methods for determining losses and efficiency of rotating electrical machines from tests are defined in IEC 60034-2-1 [16]. In IEC 60034-2-1 the tests are grouped into three main approaches: direct, indirect, and back-to-back power measurements. These measurements are the base for the efficiency determination.

3.1 State of the art

A detailed analysis of different efficiency determination methods has been conducted in the project deliverable D1 and are summarized below:

- The calorimetric method uses the advantage of accurate power loss measurements and quantifies the power losses in form of heat. It is well-suited for validating small efficiency improvements, especially when they are close to 100% efficiency, owing to its low errors, typically below 0.5%. However, when it comes to determining the efficiency of full-size multi-megawatt nacelles, this approach is not practical. This impracticality stems from the considerable time required to achieve a stable temperature at the current operating point, and the create a housing for a full-size nacelle pose significant challenges.
- The indirect method or the back-to-back efficiency determination method in [17] [18] for determining efficiency can be used for specimens of all sizes without having dramatical price increases or technical restrictions since no accurate mechanical measurement is needed. It involves the separation of losses along with linked temperature corrections. It may not be feasible for all nacelles on test benches because this method is rather time-consuming as all operation points have to be met twice. Another disadvantage is the temperature-dependence of some loss types, e.g., stator winding losses. Consequently, the temperature of the DUT should be as equal as possible in both power flow directions. Moreover, not all NTBs can be run in reverse mode.

This therefore leads to a high accuracy of the mechanical power measurement as the direct efficiency determination method needs to be deployed. Here, the efficiency of electrical machines, η , is defined as the ratio of useful output, P_{out} , to total input, P_{in} :

$$\eta = \frac{P_{\text{out}}}{P_{\text{in}}} = \frac{P_{\text{el}}}{P_{\text{me}}} \quad (1)$$

3.2 iso-efficiency contours

The iso-efficiency contours, also known as efficiency maps, have been used to characterize the efficiency of motors operated by variable speed drives across their entire operational spectrum, as detailed in references [19], [20] and [21]. In this approach, the efficiency values for each operational point are determined using the direct method, which involves precise measurements of mechanical output power and electrical input power, along with monitoring the quality of the supply voltage. These measurements serve as the basis for calculating the iso-efficiency contours, as depicted in Figure 5.

This methodology has already found application in combustion engines and electric vehicle drivetrains. Determining the number of measurement points involves finding a balance between the accuracy of the iso-efficiency contours and the measurement effort. Like the direct efficiency determination according to IEC 60034-2-1, these measurements are conducted under steady-state conditions, meaning the motor operates at a constant speed and a constant torque load. To achieve this stable state, the motor operates at its rated values. Additionally, a temperature variation of up to 5 K is allowed during the measurements.

It was observed in reference [20] that there are more significant efficiency gradients in the lower speed and torque regions, requiring a greater number of measurement points in this range. Consequently, the distribution of measurement points across the motor's operational range may not be uniform. [19, 20, 21]

Figure 5: Analytical iso-efficiency contour example of an induction motor with 4 kW, 400 V, and a rated speed of 1500 min^{-1} taken from [20].

4 Measurement procedure

In the case of wind turbines, overall efficiency is influenced by a multitude of components and factors, including the gearbox, generator, transformer, converter, filters, bearings, control algorithms, and the cooling system. To optimize the interaction of all these components and determine the highest efficiency, it's beneficial to adapt the concept of the iso-efficiency contours for assessing the efficiency of nacelles on test benches. Furthermore, during the measurement procedure, certain steps and rules should be followed to ensure the sensors are working close to the calibration conditions. In this way, the measured efficiency can be trusted to be in the guaranteed uncertainty interval.

4.1 The application of iso-efficiency contours

The newly developed load profile for efficiency determination is based on standardised efficiency determination methods, which are a combination of rotational speed and applied torque. The number of both rotational speed and torque levels depends on the total operating range of the DUT. The overall measuring range is specified accordingly by the DUT. Just like the well-known standards, the torque is always applied in descending order, i.e., from the largest to the smallest torque. The rotational speed can be approached both in ascending and descending order; for these measurements, the rotational speed was approached in an increasing manner.

If measurements are interrupted, particularly when torque or rotational speed is increasing (decreasing), it is important to restart the measurements from the previous lowest (highest) point of torque or rotational speed. In instances where there is negative torque, which could occur during an emergency brake event (referred to as torque inversion), the measurement setup should be pre-loaded with maximum torque and maximum rotational speed before resuming the measurements. This pre-loading is done to eliminate any mechanical remanence effects.

(a) iso-efficiency load profile.

(b) Load point overview / operating range.

Figure 6: Newly developed iso-efficiency load profile (a) and overview (b) of all performed measurement points used for the iso-efficiency map determination adapted to the boundary conditions of the DUT.

The new load profile is accurate, fast, and cost-effective with its full-range testing of wind turbines including converter performance.

When there are no particular operating points for which the efficiency needs to be determined, such as typical maximum power, the operating points should be spread evenly. Attention is to be paid to omitting operational points close to eigenfrequencies of the system, which would lead to undesired dynamic or instable control effects. Due to the large dimensions and the complexity of wind turbine drive trains, it is not possible to measure in the thermal equilibrium state of the drive train.

4.2 Measurement interval / data evaluation

When conducting rotational measurements, dynamic effects occur in the form of torque ripples. These ripples have various causes, including the inherent excitation and design of rotating electrical machines,

as well as changes in the air gap due to the substantial weight under rotation. On the measurement side, factors like the deadweight effect (resulting from horizontal transducer mounting) and misalignment errors such as eccentricity, non-parallelism, and drivetrain tilting contribute to these ripples as well.

Evaluating these dynamic effects necessitates continuous recording for each operating point. To ensure accurate measurements, it is crucial to wait until stable working conditions are achieved before taking values at a specific operating point. For the Low-Speed Shaft (LSS), torque signal averaging over an integer number of revolutions helps mitigate these effects.

In Figure 10, torque and rotational speed ripples with a 90° delay, as measured in the 4 MW NTB of the CWD at RWTH Aachen, are depicted. To account for the influence of torque ripples, it is recommended to average the torque signal during rotation over six revolutions for each operating point [22]. The ideal number of revolutions should be as high as possible while still maintaining reasonable measurement times for each load step, and the choice of six revolutions strikes a balance between measurement time and measurement quality. To quantify and consider instability as a contributor to measurement uncertainty, a minimum of four revolutions should be acquired.

Figure 7: Real measurement data from a test bench for wind turbine drive trains; here the instability in the torque as well as in the rotational speed measurement over six full revolutions can be clearly seen.

On the High-Speed Shaft (HSS), as a large number of rotations occur within a short time, averaging over an exact number of revolutions is not necessary. Instead, averaging can be performed over a fixed time interval from 8 seconds.

4.3 Preloading

Before conducting each measurement, it is necessary to preload the torque measuring devices with the nominal torque for approximately five minutes in the measurement direction. This preloading serves the purpose of alleviating the sensor body from the influence of remanence, which represents any remaining deformation and stress resulting from prior loading. Remanence effects are notably observable when the transducer has previously experienced loading in the opposite direction. This can occur through rotated installation, intentional anti-clockwise loading (as seen in static calibrations), or in the event of an emergency stop on the test bench. Detailed information on the impact of remanence on the zero signal can be found in D4 [10].

Ideally, there should be no interruption between the preloading phase and the actual measurement. Following an emergency stop, it is also essential to perform a preload with the nominal torque in the direction of rotation before proceeding with further measurements. The zero signal used for taring should only be determined after the preloading process. In cases where preloading cannot be executed, remanence should be considered as an additional factor contributing to the overall measurement uncertainty. Typically, an initial preloading should be carried out when the setup is first put into operation to minimize the influence of remanence.

4.4 Zero signal determination

After the preloading, the torque zero signal with no load applied is to be determined and subsequently used to tare the measurement signal. This is necessary because torque sensors, which are based on the measuring principle of strain gauges, always have an offset. This offset can change slightly due to the installation in the drive train and is position-dependent when installed horizontally. In order to obtain a suitable, position-independent zero signal, the zero signal is recorded in at least four static positions (twelve positions are recommended), evenly distributed over a full revolution of the drive train, and the mean value of the values is calculated as the zero offset. This signal offset M_{zero} needs to be determined at the beginning of each measurement day, then used in the post-processing to tare the torque signal M_s of all measurements:

$$M = M_s - M_{zero} \quad (2)$$

The accuracy of the zero offset directly impacts torque measurement. Having a greater number of measurement positions results in a clearer distribution of the offset at various angle positions, leading to a more accurate determination of the mean offset value. Figure 8 shows the torque zero offset measured at 12 evenly distributed shaft positions in three different days on an NTB. Although this measurement can be time consuming to perform on each measurement day, the risk of measuring only very few positions cannot be easily neglected.

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Figure 8: Real measurement data from a test bench for wind turbine drive trains; here the distribution of the torque zero offset can be clearly seen.

4.5 Rotational speed measurement

In NTBs, rotary incremental encoders serve as the most frequently used rotational speed transducers. These encoders measure shaft rotational speed by counting the optical or magnetic increments, which generate voltage pulses as the shaft rotates. The frequency of the pulses is directly proportional to the shaft's rotational speed. Subsequently, the DAQ system processes the signal by counting the number of pulses within a specified time interval. Additionally, the direction of rotation can be determined by generating two pulse signals with a 90° phase shift. By marking a start point as the reference position, it becomes also possible to measure the absolute angle position.

Two critical factors influence the measurement accuracy of rotary encoders based on these principles:

- Pulse count accuracy: To ensure accurate pulse counting, the pulse period must be significantly smaller than the measurement interval. Achieving this requires the encoder to have a large number of increments along its circumference. The specific increment count required depends on the operational rotational speed range. For the LSS, which rotates slowly, more increments are typically needed. Conversely, on the HSS where the rotation is much faster, fewer

increments can be also sufficient. In the end, the encoder-generated signal frequency is expected to be at least in the kilohertz range.

- Increment distribution: The accuracy of the encoder also depends on correctly knowing the number of increments along the shaft's circumference. For cases where absolute shaft angle or transient speed measurements are involved, it's important for the increments to also be evenly distributed along the circumference.

To ensure that both criteria of the encoder are met, it is advisable to perform an in-situ calibration of the encoder using a reference system, such as an inclinometer. In addition, a guideline for external calibration of angular encoders has been published by EURAMET.

4.6 Mechanical power measurement

Rotational mechanical power represents the rate at which mechanical energy is transferred within a rotating system. In the context of NTBs, it quantifies how rapidly input energy is transferred from the nacelle's LSS and, if applicable, the HSS into the DUT.

Mathematically, rotational mechanical power is calculated by multiplying the torque applied to the shaft by the shaft's angular velocity. The average mechanical power (P_{me}) within a measurement interval (T_{me}) can be expressed as:

$$P_{me} = \frac{1}{T_{me}} \cdot \frac{2\pi}{60} \int_0^{T_{me}} M(t) \cdot n(t) dt, \quad (3)$$

where the transient value of torque $M(t)$ and rotational speed $n(t)$ are first multiplied and then averaged over the desired time period. Since min^{-1} is commonly used for electrical machines instead of the SI unit rad/s , a converting factor $\frac{2\pi}{60}$ is added.

In practical applications, to minimize the impact of periodic oscillations, torque and speed are separately averaged over an integer number of drivetrain revolutions. The ideal number of revolutions should be as high as possible while still maintaining reasonable measurement times for each load step. This leads to an adapted expression:

$$P_{me,ad} = \frac{1}{T_{me}^2} \cdot \frac{2\pi}{60} \int_0^{T_{me}} M(t) dt \cdot \int_0^{T_{me}} n(t) dt. \quad (4)$$

It is essential to note that (4) is valid only when torque and rotational speed remain constant. In practice, torque and speed have dynamic ripples, and the applicability of this equation can be quantified through an averaging error $e_{P_{me}\%}$:

$$e_{P_{me}\%} = \frac{P_{me,ad} - P_{me}}{P_{me}} \cdot 100\%. \quad (5)$$

Fortunately, the research in [23] indicates that the averaging error ($e_{P_{m}\%}$) is generally small and negligible in most practical use cases. However, this error is closely linked to the ratio and phase shift of ripples in torque and speed. It should be particularly considered when dealing with high torque ripples. To perform this analysis effectively, measurements should not only involve averaged values using a power analyser but also verify the transient values in the high frequency range.

4.7 Electrical power measurement

The electrical output power is calculated as the sum of the power of the three phases determined by the transient current and voltage as in (6). A detailed analysis of electrical power determination methods is presented in the D6 [14].

$$P_{el} = P_{el,p1} + P_{el,p2} + P_{el,p3} = \frac{1}{T_{el}} \left(\int_0^{T_{el}} u_1(t) \cdot i_1(t) dt + \int_0^{T_{el}} u_2(t) \cdot i_2(t) dt + \int_0^{T_{el}} u_3(t) \cdot i_3(t) dt \right) \quad (6)$$

The first measurement approach is to measure the current and voltage signals in each phase to calculate the electrical power as in (6) in real time or in the post processing. This will require a relatively high sampling rate that depends on the frequency of the signal to be measured to ensure the measurement

quality. At the same time, the recorded data is substantial in size. A key advantage in this approach is the preservation of transient signals for further analysis.

The second approach is using a power analyser, in which the calculation of electrical power as in (6) is performed automatically online. While the calculation is utilizing the current and voltage signals measured in MHz range, only the averaged values within a defined measurement interval are recorded. Implementing these strategies will lead to reduced measurement data volume while preserving measurement accuracy.

To eliminate measurement errors, the electrical signals are synchronously averaged over the same period as applied for mechanical power within the same measurement interval:

$$T_{me} = T_{el}. \quad (7)$$

4.8 Efficiency determination

For DUTs on NTBs, the energy efficiency is assessed by measuring the electrical output power, P_{el} , which is the sum of three phase power, $P_{el,p1...3}$, and the mechanical input power, P_{me} , which is the product of torque, M , and rotational speed, n :

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{P_{el,p1} + P_{el,p2} + P_{el,p3}}{P_{me}} \quad (8)$$

In addition to the overall system efficiency, the efficiency of the individual components can also be determined by measuring the power flow between each component.

4.9 Temperature dependency

Since the temperature change has a strong influence on the drivetrain efficiency for NTBs, the efficiency is supposed to be measured at thermal static condition. In practice, however, the considerable time required to achieve a stable temperature at each current operating point is over hours, is impractical to perform due to the time cost. To clearly identify the influence of temperature on the DUT efficiency, it is essential to ensure that all sequentially conducted measurements within the iso-efficiency contours are completed by the corresponding temperature information.

For a further analysis, a heat run can be performed on the drive train. A heat run is dedicated to defining the warming up time of all mechanical components at maximum rotational speed and at a maximum torque. To monitor the temperature influence on the torque signals, a permanent data recording is necessary. The measuring time for this test is at least four hours. This measurement is supposed to be used to analyse the temperature influence on the efficiency. A practical example is presented in Figure

9.

Figure 9: Heat run test on NTB at CWD of RWTH University to evaluate gearbox efficiency in relation to temperature.

5 Measurement uncertainty

A comprehensive measurement includes not just the measured values but also the corresponding expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU). This section delves into the uncertainties associated with all measured parameters linked to the assessment of system efficiency, which can be divided into calibrated uncertainties, condition dependent uncertainties and the derived uncertainties.

5.1 Calibrated uncertainties

The calibrated MUs presented in Table 3 can be directly obtained after the in-situ calibration in section 2.2. The calibration results of the voltage and current measurements are given as the sensitivity corrections and the corresponding measurement uncertainty for the RMS values and phase values. As (6) uses the transient measurement values, the calibration results are not directly applicable here. Since the aim of the project is focused on the primary electrical power on the grid side, where the fundamental 50 Hz is the dominant frequency part with a power factor close to 1, only the uncertainty for the RMS values calibrated at 50 Hz is considered as uncertainty contribution.

Table 3: Overview of calibrated MU for efficiency determination

Expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU) sources	Absolute quantity	Relative quantity	Distribution type
Torque measurement ($k=2$)	$U_{M,cali}$	$W_{M,cali}$	Normal
Rotational speed measurement ($k=2$)	U_n	W_n	Normal
Voltage amplitude measurement ($k=2$)	U_U	W_U	Normal
Current amplitude measurement ($k=2$)	U_I	W_I	Normal

5.2 Condition-dependent uncertainties

Condition-dependent uncertainties presented in Table 4 are those uncertainty contributions that fluctuate with changing environmental conditions and, as a result, difficult to be included for during the calibration phase.

Table 4: Overview of condition-dependent uncertainties for efficiency determination

Expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU) sources	Absolute quantity	Relative quantity	Distribution type
Torque zero offset measurement ($k=2$)	$U_{M,zero}$	$W_{M,zero}$	Normal
Operating point instability in efficiency measurement ($k=2$)	$U_{\eta,in}$	$W_{\eta,in}$	Normal

As the torque zero offset is determined as the average value of the static torque signal measured at N_{zero} number of different positions. The MU ($k=2$) of this averaging process is calculated based on the standard deviation of the distributions, reduced by the number of repeat measurements N_{zero} :

$$U_{M,zero} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{N_{zero}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{zero}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{zero}} (M_{zero,i} - \bar{M}_{zero})^2}, \quad (9)$$

and the corresponding relative MU is calculated with the reference of the current torque load:

$$W_{M,zero} = \frac{U_{M,zero}}{M}. \quad (10)$$

The other condition-dependent uncertainty comes from the operating point instability as mentioned in section 4.2. The data presented in Figure 10 clearly indicates that at higher torque steps, there is minimal variation in torque for each revolution, resulting in minimal periodic fluctuations in rotational speed and generator output power. In contrast, at lower torque steps, the oscillation ratio of torque becomes more pronounced. This highlights a more significant instability in the load step in the lower torque range, likely attributed to the control system's behaviour. For instance, during the 5th revolution, the control system substantially increased the torque to address the decrease in rotational speed. As a consequence, the torque exhibits a greater degree of variation compared to higher torque steps [22].

Figure 10: Torque and speed signal ripples (smoothed with a moving mean of 150 points for one second for better visualisation) over six full revolutions with a phase shift of 90° to each other at 1.5 MN m and 12.5 min⁻¹(top) and at 150 kN m at 17.5 min⁻¹ (bottom) [22].

To quantify the operating point instability, the expanded measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) is calculated based on the standard deviation of the distribution of the N_{rev} number of measured full revolutions:

$$U_{\eta,in} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{rev}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{rev}} (\eta_{rev} - \bar{\eta}_{rev})^2}, \quad (11)$$

and the corresponding relative MU is also calculated with the reference of the current torque load:

$$W_{\eta,in} = \frac{U_{\eta,in}}{M}. \quad (12)$$

5.3 Derived uncertainties

Base on the calibrated and determined MU from each contribution sources so far, the desired MU for the output variables such as mechanical and electrical power, as well as the efficiency (presented in Table 5) can be derived using the basic model established in the Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) from [24].

Table 5: Overview of derived uncertainties for efficiency determination

Expanded Measurement Uncertainty (MU) sources	Absolute quantity	Relative quantity	Distribution type
Mechanical power measurement ($k=2$)	U_{me}	W_{me}	Normal
Electrical power measurement ($k=2$)	U_{el}	W_{el}	Normal
Efficiency determination ($k=2$)	U_{η}	W_{η}	Normal

Base on the basic equation for mechanical power determination:

$$P_{me} = 2\pi(M_s - M_{zero}) \cdot n, \quad (13)$$

the expanded absolute uncertainty ($k=2$) for mechanical power measurement can be estimated as:

$$U_{me}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial M_s} \cdot U_{M,cali} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial M_{zero}} \cdot U_{M,zero} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{me}}{\partial n} \cdot U_n \right)^2. \quad (14)$$

After mathematical conversion, the expanded relative uncertainty ($k=2$) for mechanical power measurement can be written as:

$$W_{me} = \sqrt{W_{M,cali}^2 + W_{M,zero}^2 + W_n^2}. \quad (15)$$

Similarly, the expanded absolute measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) for electrical power measurement can be estimated from the measurement on all three phases:

$$U_{el}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial u_1} \cdot U_{U_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial i_1} \cdot U_{I_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial u_2} \cdot U_{U_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial i_2} \cdot U_{I_2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial u_3} \cdot U_{U_3} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial P_{el}}{\partial i_3} \cdot U_{I_3} \right)^2. \quad (16)$$

By assuming that the power among all three phases is symmetrical and the sensors for each phase are identically accurate, the expanded relative measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) for electrical power measurement can be simplified as:

$$W_{Pe} = \frac{\sqrt{W_I^2 + W_U^2}}{\sqrt{3}}. \quad (17)$$

Finally, for the expanded relative measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) for efficiency determination, as aforementioned, the operating point instability contribute also to the total MU beside the electrical and mechanical power measurement:

$$W_{\eta} = \sqrt{W_{me}^2 + W_{el}^2 + W_{\eta,in}^2}. \quad (18)$$

6 Benefit for users

By conducting the presented in-situ calibrations, test bench operators can benefit from knowing the deviation between their internal measuring instrument and a traced national standard and correcting for this deviation to obtain a more accurate efficiency measurement result. By following this good practice guide for efficiency determination, the efficiency of DUTs can be determined more reliably within an uncertainty interval.

A convincing example has been given by the measurements in [25], where the efficiency of a 2.75 MW nacelle is compared using an uncalibrated measurement device and a corrected signal after calibration. The results show that especially calibration of mechanical input is important, as the torque measurement is off by about 5 % and results in significantly lower system efficiencies, as in Figure 11. Although as expected, torque measurement has contributed the largest part of the uncertainty. Surprisingly, the electrical power measurement can also contribute a large part to the uncertainty, if the sensors are not carefully selected.

Figure 11: Efficiency determination using calibrated and uncalibrated measurement devices. [25]

Finally, three practical measurements on different test benches have been conducted, following the guidelines outlined in this best practice guide, for the reference of readers:

- Z. Song *et al.* Traceable efficiency determination of a 2.75 MW nacelle on a test bench. *Forsch Ingenieurwes* 87, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10010-023-00650-1>, 259–273 (2023).
- H. Zhang *et al.* State-of-the-art efficiency determination of a wind turbine powertrain on a nacelle test bench (to be published).
- N. Yogal *et al.* Validation of a traceable efficiency determination method for wind turbines with a focus on measurement uncertainty (to be published).

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VIII Acronyms

cm	characterisation map
CR	control room
CWD	Center for Wind Power Drives
DAQ	data acquisition
DFIG	doubly fed induction generator
DUT	device under test
DyNaLab	dynamic nacelle testing laboratory
EMPIR	European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research
EPMS	electrical power measurement system
EU	European Union
EURAMET	The European Association of National Metrology Institutes
FhG IWES	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft - Institut für Windenergiesysteme
FVA	Forschungsvereinigung Antriebstechnik e. V.
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HSS	high-speed shaft
IRIG-B	inter range instrumentation group timecode B
JB	junction box
LAS	load application system
LSS	low-speed shaft
LV	low voltage
MEMS	Micro-electromechanical Systems
MPTS	mechanical power transfer standard
MV	medium voltage
NTB	nacelle system test bench
NTL	non-torque loading
NTP	network time protocol
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
PTP	precision time protocol
PWM	pulse-width modulation
RMS	root mean square
RPMS	reference power measurement system
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
THD	total harmonic distortion
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
WindEFCY	Wind efficiency

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